

Socio-economic impact of remittances from Italy: An empirical study of rural household head relation to the migrant in Bangladesh

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Abstract-

This paper analysed the effect of the relation of the household head to the migrant amongst 10 villages on the remittance determinants and their socioeconomic impacts of remittance receiving households in rural Bangladesh. Using micro-economic data from a survey conducted in 2013, statistical analysis was carried out on 300 rural households. The empirical findings provided that the household head relation to the migrant such as father, mother, wife and brother has variation of remittance determinants and their socioeconomic impact in rural area at the origin. The household unit analysis also showed that remittance determinants and socio-economic impact vary from household head relation at the same community level of households. Moreover, relationship between the socioeconomic impact from remittance and demographic determinants also vary due to the household head relationship discrimination among the same rural area at the origin country.

Index Terms -remittance, household head, father, mother, wife, brother, rural household

JEL classification: A12, B21, C51, C81, D19, J19, R23

Introduction

Bangladeshi migrants in Italy are predominantly single and male migrants who are living under 'transnationally split' (Yeoh, Graham, and Boyle, 2002) conditions and obligated to maintain economic and social relations with their family members back home (Rahman and Kabir, 2012). The obligation of maintaining sustained economic and social ties with home stems from the dominance of the household in the social and economic affairs of the Bangladeshi society and their transnational household members. Individual migrant is deeply enmeshed in a complex web of household relations and dependencies: He/she moves internationally for work as an envoy of the extended household that places the well-being of the extended family above the individual migrant's interests (Rahman, 2011). Whether it is temporary labour migration such as migration to the Middle East or more permanent form of migration such as migration to Italy, maintaining sustained economic relations with left behind households remain one of the key priorities for migrant members (Ullah, 2010, Rahman 2009). This is comprehensive evidenced in the annual inflow of remittances to Bangladesh, which has increased from around \$4.2 billion in 2005 to nearly \$10.9 billion in 2013 (BMET, 2014).

According to the World Bank (2014) 'remittances to developing countries are estimated at \$404 billion in 2013, up 3.5 percent compared with 2012. Growth in

remittance flows to developing countries is expected to accelerate to an annual average of 8.4 percent over the next three years, raising flows to \$436 billion in 2014 and \$516 billion in 2016'. These facts and figures indicate that international migration and remittance is an intricate phenomenon, the dynamics of which are increasingly turning a drastic policy topic global economic, social, legal and cultural topic (Mannan and Farhana, 2014).

Objective of the study

Based on the research questions this research has three objectives.

1. To examine the socio-economic impact of remittances at the left behind rural household of the Bangladeshi households receiving remittance from their family members working in Italy.
2. To explore the relationship between socio-demographic factors and the household relation to the migrant.
3. To investigate the socioeconomic impact of such remittances of all relation at the household heads at the left behind households in Bangladesh.

Methodology

This study chose a quantitative method approach as its methodology to accommodate method for an explanation of the research objectives.

Selection of survey village and course of the survey

In line with the study focus, the selection of the study area in Bangladesh was based on the high incidence of household members migrating to Italy at the sub-district level (Upazila) and the prevalence of remittance-receiving households at the sub-sub-district level (Union Parisad). Shariatpur is located in the Dhaka division and in the greater Faridpur District. Among the households, a significant number of migrants are from Naria Upazila, Shariatpur District. Naria sub-district has 14 sub-sub-districts and Vogeshore union one of the sub-sub-districts, has been selected randomly for census data because there is no available published data on Bangladeshi migrant workers in Italy. Emigration from Bangladesh to Italy is predominantly a rural phenomenon. Therefore, the fieldwork undertaken for this research consists of an ethnographic village study in Bangladesh with particular reference to remittance sending migrant worker in Italy to bridge the micro and macro paradigms of migration and remittance, and offer analytical insights into the determinants and impacts of such remittance. In selecting a representative sample of the population, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) recommendation was accepted in this study. After categorising the household migrant members in Italy a random sample of 300 households was selected, the share in each village corresponding to their proportion in the whole population (the remittance received household).

Ethical Issues

This research was conducted in compliance with the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007) and was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Southern Cross University (Approval Number ECN-13-141).

Construction impact variable to determine socioeconomic impact

The measuring instrument consisted of matrix questions to be answered by employing the four point Likert scale at the questionnaire. The socioeconomic impact variable comprises more than one item and various respondent categories. From the descriptive or univariate analysis, the each item or statement is studied by tabulating the frequency distribution table and calculating the respective percentage of the answer. In bivariate analysis, every single item in the

matrix question is cross-tabulated with the respective answer variable which is completely long and difficult. Further, it might not be significant or yet not complete the aims of the research. To defeat this matter, an index variable is commonly created to the study the associated outcome of all the items in forecasting the response variable. In this context, all ascertains in the matrix questions are compiled simultaneously to all form an index variable.

Nevertheless, at first the index variable is developed, consistency within all the items in the question matrix has to free from the doubts. In this context, a reliability check is performed, and the value of Cronbach's Alpha is determined. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 16.0) enhances this facility using an analysis menu, pursued by sub-menu scale that includes the reliability analysis test. Whether, by the reliability check, the value of Alpha keeps within the range of 0.7 to 1.0, all of the statements in the question matrix can be complied to create an index variable. However, if the value of Alpha is lower than 0.7, the component of consistency between diverse statements is determined individually, and poorer one are cropped from the index variable to raise the value of Alpha. On authorisation of consistency component, the scores on every item in a question matrix listed with the help of responses categories are summed up. The minimum and maximum values are ascertained by sub-menu descriptive statistics pursued by frequencies. The minimum values are deducted from the maximum values, and the residuals are divided by the number of categories in the index variable.

In order to study the associated outcome of the after remittance amenities was represented by the participants' assertions on the aggregate variable "socioeconomic impact from remittances" an index variable was created. A reliability test provided the value of Cronbach's Alpha (0.842) that ensured the availability of consistency components in all the statements. Therefore, they can be combined to create a single assertion describing benefits obtained after remittances received. In this context, the score of all statements was summed up and the minimum score attributed in the matrix question was 5 (five) whereas the maximum score was 15 (fifteen). The score range from 5 to 15 was transfigured into three ranges of answers. Score 5 to 8 is grouped as "low" outcome, range 9 to 12 namely "medium", and 13 to 16 as "strong". The three categories (low, medium and

strong) reveal the strength of socioeconomic benefits from the remittances. Descriptive statistics were used to ascertain the mean score and the standard deviation, which were counted as 11.0933 and 2.46676 respectively.

Results

The cross tabulation of the household participants survey response about the remittance receiver household head relation to the migrant and remittance

indicates in the table 1.1 and the results shows that the majority (43.0%) household head were father, 32% wife, 15% mother and 10% brother. All relation to the migrants were received various ranges of remittances. The 3% of wife were received the highest range of remittances BDT 14,00,001 to 15,00,000, 3 % of mother BDT11,00,001-12,00,000, 3% father BDT 9,00,001-10,00,000, and 6% brother BDT 7,00,001 to 8,00,000. It also shows that the father relation to migrant household like receive highest percentage of remittances.

Table 1.1: Cross Tabulation Household yearly remittance received and household head relation to migrant

Household yearly remittance received (BDT)	Household Head Relation to Migrant				Total
	Father	Mother	Wife	Brother	
1,00,001-2,00,000	21	6	6	3	36
2,00,001-3,00,000	9	12	9	6	36
3,00,001-4,00,000	9	3	6	0	18
4,00,001-5,00,000	6	0	12	0	18
5,00,001-6,00,000	33	15	12	6	66
6,00,001-7,00,000	24	6	9	9	48
7,00,001-800,000	21	0	18	6	45
8,00,001-900,000	3	0	0	0	3
9,00,001-10,00,000	3	0	6	0	9
11,00,001-12,00,000	0	3	12	0	15
13,00,001-14,00,000	0	0	3	0	3
14,00,001-15,00,000	0	0	3	0	3
Total	129	45	96	30	300
% of Total	43.0%	15.0%	32.0%	10.0%	100.0%

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

However, as depicted in the figure 1.1 also indicates that father relation to the migrant household head highest (26%) remittances range BDT 9,00,001 to 10, 00,000 and maximum percentage (26%) father relation to the migrant household head were received BDT 500,001 to 600,000 yearly remittances from their migrant son at the destination.

Figure 1.1: Distribution of father relation to migrant remittance receiving household head

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Changes socioeconomic status over all households

The socioeconomic impacts acquired by the migrants’ households left behind in rural Bangladesh were examined in this study. The highest number of the respondents reported an improvement in all four indicators of remittances benefits, namely improvement of children’s education and improvement of housing condition. Table 1.2 shows that 56.0% and 41.0% reported an improvement of housing and children’s education to a great extent respectively. However, 16.3 % and 13.0% got a more social and family network extended in the community and society respectively as well as other improvement also reported 6.7% increase of living standard, 6% household members’ employment opportunity and 4.0% savings were to a great extent.

Table 1.2: Socio-economic impact at the household for all the households in 10 rural villages

Socioeconomic impact	To great extent		To reasonable extent		To some extent		No Change	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improve children’s education	123	41.0	99	33.0	30	10.0	48	16.0
Improve housing condition	168	56.0	72	24.0	60	20.0	-----	-----
Employment opportunity	18	6.0	84	28.0	18	6.0	180	60.0
Increase living standards	21	7.0	195	65.0	84	28.0	-----	-----
Financial stability	6	2.0	210	70.0	84	28.0	-----	-----
Extend family networks	39	13.0	163	54.3	98	32.7	-----	-----
Extend social networks	49	16.3	152	50.7	99	33.0	-----	-----
Savings	12	4.0	201	67.0	84	28.0	3	1.0
To increase social status	-----	-----	36	12.0	261	87.0	3	1.0
To help relatives	12	4.0	69	23.0	219	73.0	-----	-----
To donate religious organisations	3	1.0	87	29.0	210	70.0	-----	-----
To saving for the future happiness	6	2.0	27	9.0	237	79.0	30	10.0
To increase business income	-----	-----	36	12.0	117	39.0	147	49.0
Illness in the family members	12	4.0	213	71.0	75	22.1	-----	-----

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Determinants of remittances and socio-economic impact over all households

Following table 1.3 explored the significance relationship among the socio-economic impact and socio-demographic characteristics of migrant, household head and household compositions. The empirical results indicated the strong relationship with migrant characteristics such as age, education, year of migration, legal status and number of visits; household head as marital status and educational attainments; household compositions showed household size, investment in financial and housing sector, living expenses and welfare.

Table 1.3: Remittances determinants associates with socio-economic impact at the household for all households in 10 rural village

	AGEm	EDUm	YMIGm	LEGSm	NVISTm	MARShh	EDUhh	HHsize	Invest_ Fin_Sec	Invest_ Hous_Dev	Ln_Live _Exp	Ln_ WelF	Loan_ Rep	SOCIO _ECO
AGEm	1	-.210**	.531**	.207**	.534**	0.031	0.076	-.152**	0.057	0.062	0.056	.210**	-0.112	-.239**
EDUm	-.210**	1	.180**	.291**	.172**	.124*	.333**	0.054	.282**	.367**	.206**	.213**	0.047	-.279**
YMIGm	.531**	.180**	1	.575**	.770**	.192**	.309**	-0.043	.346**	.414**	.334**	.419**	-.187**	-.414**
LEGSm	.207**	.291**	.575**	1	.568**	.201**	.246**	0.096	.393**	.660**	.387**	.425**	0.103	-.497**
NVISTm	.534**	.172**	.770**	.568**	1	0.113	.240**	0.006	.373**	.418**	.375**	.502**	-.187**	-.469**
MARShh	0.031	.124*	.192**	.201**	0.113	1	.528**	0.012	.178**	.279**	.203**	.194**	-0.068	-.128*
EDUhh	0.076	.333**	.309**	.246**	.240**	.528**	1	-0.08	.437**	.301**	.232**	.268**	0.071	-.164**
HHsize	-.152**	0.054	-0.043	0.096	0.006	0.012	-0.08	1	0.018	.176**	.327**	.308**	0.074	-.129*
Invest_Fin_Sec	0.057	.282**	.346**	.393**	.373**	.178**	.437**	0.018	1	.416**	.390**	.476**	0.019	-.354**
Invest_Hous_Dev	0.062	.367**	.414**	.660**	.418**	.279**	.301**	.176**	.416**	1	.374**	.346**	0.029	-.500**
Ln_Live_Exp	0.056	.206**	.334**	.387**	.375**	.203**	.232**	.327**	.390**	.374**	1	.799**	-0.054	-.320**
Ln_WelF	.210**	.213**	.419**	.425**	.502**	.194**	.268**	.308**	.476**	.346**	.799**	1	-0.073	-.430**
Loan_Rep	-0.112	0.047	-.187**	0.103	-.187**	-0.068	0.071	0.074	0.019	0.029	-0.054	-0.073	1	.149**
SOCIO_ECO	-.239**	-.279**	-.414**	-.497**	-.469**	-.128*	-.164**	-.129*	-.354**	-.500**	-.320**	-.430**	.149**	1

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Unit Analysis-Household relation to the migrant-Household head as a father:

The socioeconomic impacts explored that the household head as a father at the table 1.4. The greatly extended was mainly improvement of housing condition (65.1%) while others few sectors also improved as children’s education (30.2%), financial stability and family network (20.9%). However, all the other sectors indicated that the improvements were increased reasonable and some extend.

Table 1.4: Socio-economic impact at the household as a father household head

Socioeconomic impact	To great extent		To reasonable extent		To some extent		No Change	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improve children’s education	39	30.2	51	39.5	15	11.6	24	18.6
Improve housing condition	84	65.1	30	23.3	15	11.6	-----	-----
Employment opportunity	9	7.0	57	44.2	15	11.6	48	37.2
Increase living standards	12	9.3	81	62.8	36	27.9	-----	-----
Financial stability	3	20.9	90	69.8	36	27.9	-----	-----
Extend family networks	27	9.2	66	51.2	36	12.3	-----	-----
Extend social networks	27	20.9	63	48.8	39	30.2	-----	-----
Savings	6	4.7	90	69.8	33	25.6	-----	-----
To increase social status	-----	-----	15	11.6	111	86.0	3	2.3
To help relatives	-----	-----	30	23.3	99	76.7	-----	-----
To donate religious organisations	-----	-----	33	25.6	96	74.4	-----	-----
To saving for the future happiness	-----	-----	6	4.7	99	76.7	24	18.6
To increase business income	-----	-----	18	14.0	84	65.1	27	20.9
Illness in the family members	-----	-----	96	74.4	33	25.6	-----	-----

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

The empirical result at the table 1.5 indicated the significance relationship among the socio-economic impact and socio-demographic characteristics of migrant, household head and household compositions. It showed the strong relationship with migrant characteristics such as age, marital status, legal status and number of visits; household head as age; household compositions explored household size, investment in housing development and welfare.

Table 1.5: Remittances determinants associates with socio-economic impact at the household as a father household head

	AGEm	MARSm	LEGSm	NVISTm	AGEhh	HHsize	Invest_Hous _Dev	Ln_WelF	SOCIO_ ECO
AGEm	1	.569**	.195*	.263**	.209*	-0.126	.307**	0.077	-.197*
MARSm	.569**	1	.393**	.468**	.256**	.197*	.467**	0.127	-.215*
LEGSm	.195*	.393**	1	.625**	.201*	0.113	.842**	.328**	-.361**
NVISTm	.263**	.468**	.625**	1	-0.096	0	.709**	.451**	-.225*
AGEhh	.209*	.256**	.201*	-0.096	1	-0.024	0.164	-.192*	-.198*
HHsize	-0.126	.197*	0.113	0	-0.024	1	0.033	.262**	-.207*
Invest_Hous_Dev	.307**	.467**	.842**	.709**	0.164	0.033	1	.266**	-.491**
Ln_WelF	0.077	0.127	.328**	.451**	-.192*	.262**	.266**	1	-.319**
SOCIO_ECO	-.197*	-.215*	-.361**	-.225*	-.198*	-.207*	-.491**	-.319**	1

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Household head as a wife:The socioeconomic impacts explored that the household head as a wife at the table 1.6. The greatly extended were mainly children education (68.8%) and improvement of housing condition (53.1%) while others few sectors also improved as family network (20.9%), social network and living standard (15%). However, all the other sectors indicated that the improvements were increased reasonable and some extend while no changes at the business income (93.8%).

Table 1.6: Socio-economic impact at the household as a wife household head

Socioeconomic impact	To great extent		To reasonable extent		To some extent		No Change	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improve children’s education	66	68.8	24	25.0	3	3.1	3	3.1
Improve housing condition	51	53.1	27	28.1	18	18.8	-----	-----
Employment opportunity	6	6.2	3	3.1	87	90.6	-----	-----
Increase living standards	15	15.6	54	56.2	27	28.1	-----	-----
Financial stability	3	3.1	69	71.9	24	25.0	-----	-----
Extend family networks	15	15.6	48	50.0	33	34.4	-----	-----
Extend social networks	30	31.2	30	31.2	36	37.5	-----	-----
Savings	6	6.2	63	65.6	27	28.1	-----	-----
To increase social status	-----	-----	12	12.5	84	87.5	-----	-----
To help relatives	9	9.4	18	18.8	69	71.9	-----	-----
To donate religious organisations	3	3.1	27	28.1	66	68.8	-----	-----
To saving for the future happiness	6	6.2	18	18.8	69	71.9	3	3.1
To increase business income	-----	-----	-----	-----	6	6.2	90	93.8
Illness in the family members	6	6.2	75	78.1	15	15.6	-----	-----

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

The empirical result at the table 1.7 indicated the significance relationship among the socio-economic impact and socio-demographic characteristics of migrant, household head and household compositions. It showed the strong relationship with migrant characteristics such as age, education, year of migration, legal status and number of visits; household head as age and education; household compositions explored household size, investment in financial, housing development, business sector, living expenses, welfare and loan repayment.

Table 1.7: Remittances determinants associates with socio-economic impact at the household as a wife household head

	AGEm	EDUm	YMIGm	LEGSm	NVISTm	AGEhh	EDUhh	Invest_Fin_Sec	Invest_Hous_Dev	Ln_Live_Exp	Invest_Busi	Ln_WelF	Loan_Rep	SOCIO_ECO
AGEm	1	-0.1	.558**	.314**	.513**	.831**	-0.023	.288**	.275**	.474**	.312**	.615**	-.259*	-.502**
EDUm	-0.1	1	.281**	.325**	.392**	-.222*	.838**	.444**	.254*	0.185	-0.056	.232*	-0.054	-.355**
YMIGm	.558**	.281**	1	.417**	.869**	.322**	.344**	.585**	.345**	.598**	.266**	.734**	-.533**	-.716**
LEGSm	.314**	.325**	.417**	1	.602**	.253*	.315**	.602**	.520**	.327**	0.176	.514**	-0.077	-.643**
NVISTm	.513**	.392**	.869**	.602**	1	.306**	.346**	.639**	.510**	.563**	.319**	.723**	-.480**	-.789**
AGEhh	.831**	-.222*	.322**	.253*	.306**	1	-0.189	.265**	.320**	.347**	0.178	.480**	0.005	-.317**
EDUhh	-0.023	.838**	.344**	.315**	.346**	-0.189	1	.579**	.261*	.207*	0.112	.215*	-0.088	-.347**
Invest_Fin_Sec	.288**	.444**	.585**	.602**	.639**	.265**	.579**	1	.584**	.350**	.335**	.503**	-.288**	-.594**
Invest_Hous_Dev	.275**	.254*	.345**	.520**	.510**	.320**	.261*	.584**	1	.274**	0.13	.355**	-0.149	-.447**
Ln_Live_Exp	.474**	0.185	.598**	.327**	.563**	.347**	.207*	.350**	.274**	1	0.045	.873**	-.420**	-.505**
Invest_Busi	.312**	-0.056	.266**	0.176	.319**	0.178	0.112	.335**	0.13	0.045	1	0.125	-.220*	-.203*
Ln_WelF	.615**	.232*	.734**	.514**	.723**	.480**	.215*	.503**	.355**	.873**	0.125	1	-.431**	-.705**
Loan_Rep	-.259*	-0.054	-.533**	-0.077	-.480**	0.005	-0.088	-.288**	-0.149	-.420**	-.220*	-.431**	1	.367**
SOCIO_ECO	-.502**	-.355**	-.716**	-.643**	-.789**	-.317**	-.347**	-.594**	-.447**	-.505**	-.203*	-.705**	.367**	1

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Household head as a mother:

The socioeconomic impacts explored that the household head as a mother at the table 1.8. The greatly extended were improvement of housing condition (33.3%) and children education (26.7%) although these sectors not as the highest number of participants while others few sectors also improved very little margin. However, all the other sectors indicated that the improvements were increased reasonable and some extend while no changes at the business income (66.7%).

Table 1.8: Socio-economic impact at the household as a mother household head

Socioeconomic impact	To great extent		To reasonable extent		To some extent		No Change	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improve children’s education	12	26.7	12	26.7	6	13.3	15	33.3
Improve housing condition	15	33.3	9	20.0	21	46.7	-----	-----
Employment opportunity	3	6.7	9	20.0	33	73.3	-----	-----
Increase living standards	-----	-----	30	66.7	15	33.3	-----	-----
Financial stability	-----	-----	27	60.0	18	40.0	-----	-----
Extend family networks	3	6.7	21	46.7	21	46.7	-----	-----
Extend social networks	6	13.3	18	40.0	21	46.7	-----	-----
Savings	-----	-----	24	53.3	18	40.0	3	6.7
To increase social status	-----	-----	6	13.3	39	86.7	-----	-----
To help relatives	3	6.7	9	20.0	33	73.3	-----	-----
To donate religious organisations	-----	-----	12	26.7	33	73.3	-----	-----
To saving for the future happiness	-----	-----	-----	-----	42	93.3	3	1.2
To increase business income	-----	-----	6	13.3	9	20.0	30	66.7
Illness in the family members	6	13.3	27	60.0	12	26.7	-----	-----

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

The empirical finding at the table 1.9 indicated the significance relationship among the socio-economic impact and socio-demographic characteristics of migrant, household head and household compositions. It showed the strong relationship with migrant characteristics such as age, year of migration, legal status and number of visits; household head as age; household compositions explored religion, investment in financial, housing development, living expenses and welfare.

Table 1.9: Remittances determinants associates with socio-economic impact at the household as a mother household head

	AGEm	YMIGm	LEGSm	NVISTm	RELhh	Invest_ Fin_Sec	Invest_ Hous_Dev	Ln_Live _Exp	Ln_Wel F	SOCIO _ECO
AGEm	1	.420**	.416**	.619**	-.367*	0.105	.347*	.305*	.583**	-.548**
YMIGm	.420**	1	.866**	.863**	-.327*	.327*	.458**	.534**	.792**	-.513**
LEGSm	.416**	.866**	1	.713**	-.378*	.614**	.577**	.542**	.794**	-.553**
NVISTm	.619**	.863**	.713**	1	-0.27	0.114	.391**	.474**	.741**	-.521**
RELhh	-.367*	-.327*	-.378*	-0.27	1	-0.286	-0.218	-.452**	-.477**	.299*
Invest_Fin_Sec	0.105	.327*	.614**	0.114	-0.286	1	.627**	.556**	.536**	-.486**
Invest_Hous_Dev	.347*	.458**	.577**	.391**	-0.218	.627**	1	.413**	.586**	-.685**
Ln_Live_Exp	.305*	.534**	.542**	.474**	-.452**	.556**	.413**	1	.792**	-.510**
Ln_WelF	.583**	.792**	.794**	.741**	-.477**	.536**	.586**	.792**	1	-.601**
SOCIO_ECO	-.548**	-.513**	-.553**	-.521**	.299*	-.486**	-.685**	-.510**	-.601**	1

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Household head as a brother:

The socioeconomic impacts explored that the household head as a brother at the table 1.10. The greatly extended were improvement of housing condition (60.0%), children education and employment opportunity (20.0%) although these sectors not as the highest number of participants while others few sectors also improved very little margin. However, all the other sectors indicated that the improvements were increased reasonable level.

Table 1.10: Socio-economic impact at the household as a brother household head

Socioeconomic impact	To great extent		To reasonable extent		To some extent		No Change	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improve children’s education	6	20.0	12	40.0	6	20.0	6	20.0
Improve housing condition	18	60.0	6	20.0	6	20.0	-----	-----
Employment opportunity	6	20.0	12	40.0	-----	-----	12	40.0
Increase living standards	-----	-----	24	80.0	6	20.0	-----	-----
Financial stability	-----	-----	24	80.0	6	20.0	-----	-----
Extend family networks	3	10.0	21	70.0	6	20.0	-----	-----
Extend social networks	3	10.0	24	80.0	3	10.0	-----	-----
Savings	-----	-----	24	80.0	6	20.0	-----	-----
To increase social status	-----	-----	3	10.0	27	80.0	-----	-----
To help relatives	-----	-----	12	40.0	18	60.0	-----	-----
To donate religious organisations	-----	-----	15	50.0	15	50.0	-----	-----
To saving for the future happiness	-----	-----	3	10.0	27	90.0	-----	-----
To increase business income	-----	-----	12	40.0	18	60.0	-----	-----
Illness in the family members	-----	-----	15	50.0	15	50.0	-----	-----

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

The empirical result at the table 1.9 showed the significance relationship among the socio-economic impact and socio-demographic characteristics of migrant, household head and household compositions. It showed the strong relationship with migrant characteristics such as legal status and number of visits; household compositions explored investment in housing development, living and welfare.

Table 1.11: Remittances determinants associates with socio-economic impact at the household as a brother household head

	LEGS _m	NVIST _m	Invest_Hous_Dev	Ln_WelF	SOCIO_ECO
LEGS _m	1	.649**	.667**	-.633**	-.509**
NVIST _m	.649**	1	0.195	-.494**	-.425*
Invest_Hous_Dev	.667**	0.195	1	-0.315	-.764**
Ln_WelF	-.633**	-.494**	-0.315	1	.371*
SOCIO_ECO	-.509**	-.425*	-.764**	.371*	1

Source: Author calculation from the survey data

Discussion

Migrant age (Osili, 2007) is one of the important determinant influencing remittance behaviour. There is a relationship between age of the migrants and the length of stay at the destination (Mejivar et al., 1998; Rodriguez, 1996), often increase income and therefore also the available pool for remittance. Higher levels of remittances are sent by individuals under younger of age compared to older migrants (de la Briere et al., 1997). But, likewise, the adjustment impact is inferred to turn as the migrant becomes older, rendering all together remittances flows lower (DeSipio, 2000). This study found the strong negative relationship between the household head as a father, mother and wife and remittances impact at the rural household while no relationship with brother.

The empirical literature on micro-level studies indicates that the education level of migrants (Agrawal and Horowitz, 1999) is linkage to the income of the migrant and the major determinant of remittance (Fonchamnyo, 2012). Lucas and Stark (1985) and Stark and Lucas (1988) show remittances as elements of a co-operative agreement, self-enforcing, agreement between the migrant and household and also remittances repayment for the cost of migration and educational expenses. According to McDonald and Valenzuela (2012), the higher the level of education of the migrant, the higher will be the level of remittances. Rapoport and Docquier (2005) explain that the education level of the migrant do not play vital role under the altruistic and exchange motives as educated

migrants have lower propensities to return but have a positive impact on remittances under the investment motive. This study revealed that the strong negative relationship with wife as a household head at the rural level to the remittances impact at the left behind households.

Several studies show that migrant marital status and residency pattern of household members, including spouses and children, are significant determinants of remittance motivation (Johnson and Whitelaw 1974; Menjivar et al. 1998; Vanwey 2004; Luke, 2007; Alba and Sugui 2009). According to Sahu and Das (2009) single migrants and married heads living alone at the destination are likely to remit more than married heads living with their spouse and children. Furthermore, remittances increase while household head becomes a grandparent or the spouse lives outside or divorced, the household head send monies to share with the number of nuclear household members living outside the household (DeVoretz and Vadean, 2007). This research explored that marital status of the migrant strongly negative correlation with the household head as a father to the socio-economic impact.

The relationship between legal status of the migrant and the remittance linkage (Holst et al.,2008, 2010, 2011; Bettin and Lucchetti, 2012). Migrant remittances and their effect on the developing economics rarely focus on the status that affect migrants’ remittance model (Mahuteau et al.,2010) typically analyse the underlying motivations to remit. As risk-averse migrants, who, in the face of higher income risk, remit

more (Amuedo-Dorantes and Pozo, 2006a) and they also find undocumented migrant likely to send monies more percentage than the documented. Markova and Reilly (2007) show a positive determinant of remittances and the strong relationship between the legal status of the migrant at the destination and remittance flow at the origin. This study found that the strong negative correlation with all relationship to the household head at the origin in terms of socio-economic impact at the rural households.

Many empirical studies explore that the number of visits to the household members influence remittance behaviour (Lerch et al., 2006). During the visit at the origin, migrant bring gifts for their household members, family, extended and fictive kin, and friends, they assert and keep up their community networks (Goldring, 1998) therefore the remittance effect direct and indirect at the home country in cash and kind. In contrast, rarely trip to the household members a lower likelihood to send remittances either cash or kind, at the same time, there is a gender and origin discrimination as (Lerch et al., 2006). Migrant who make frequent visits at the origin, not only to sustain community liaison, but also to lead or to constitute critical economic linkages (Kemper, 1981). This paper revealed that the number of visits by the migrant strong negatively correlated to the all four level of relationship to the household head and socio-economic impact at the origin.

Age of the household head is one of important determinant which play vital role in the remittance behaviour and the age factor also vary from country to country (DeVoretz and Vadean, 2008). Age of the household head nexus with gender behaviour in the remittance motive, for example male household less like to receive remittance rather than female (McDonald and Valenzuela, 2012). However, Germenji et al (2001) show the older household head receive more remittance than the younger household head which reveal that the adult children care for their old parents as well their grant parents. This study explored that the age of household head strongly negative correlation while the relationship to the migrant as father and wife in terms of socio-economic impact at the household.

Higher education levels of the household head may reflect better household resources and income opportunities and so less economic need from overseas

income, therefore the educational attainment of the household head not significant with remittance amount and such provide some support the altruism motive (McDonald and Valenzuela, 2012). However, this study revealed that the educational level of household head also negatively correlated with the relationship as a wife for socio-economic impact at the left behind rural household.

Conclusion

The present study investigated the household head relation to the migrant such as father, mother, wife and brother and the variation of remittance determinants and their socioeconomic impact in rural area at the origin. The findings provided valuable discrimination among the relationship of the household heads. The household unit analysis show that remittance determinants and socio-economic impact vary from household head relation at the same community level of households. Moreover, relationship between the socioeconomic impact from remittance and demographic determinants also vary due to the household head relationship discrimination among the same rural area at the origin country.

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